

DATA ON 2-(4-DIETHYLAMINO-1-METHYL BUTYLAMINO)-3-METHYL-5,8-DIMETHOXY QUINOXALINE (II)

Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analytical					
			Caled %			Found %		
			C	H	N	C	H	N
(v) C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ (a) (s)	115-16 (s)	70	66.66	8.88	15.5	66.16	8.39	15.25

a = method used for synthesis.

S = Benzene-Pet. ether (60-80°) mixture (1:1).

Acknowledgement

Authors thank M/S. Bristol Laboratories, Syracuse, N. Y., U. S. A., for antiprotozoal testing of our compounds.

References

- O. GAWRON and P. E. SPOERRI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 514.
- A. B. SEN and O. P. MADAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 225.
- J.F. RYLEY and G.J. STACEY, *Parasitology*, 1963, 53, 303.
- H. N. PRINCE, E. GRUNBERG, E. TITSWORTH and W. F. LORENZO, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1969, 18, 728.
- S. J. POWELL, A. J. WILMOTT and R. ELSDON DEW, *Annab. Trop. Med. and Parasitol.*, 1967, 61, 511.
- F.Y. WISELOGLE, *A survey of Antimalarial Drugs*, 1941-45, Edwards, Ann. Arbor, Mich, 1946.
- W. SCHULEMANN, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Med.*, 1932, 25, 897.
- G. R. COATNEY, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1963, 12, 121.
- R. G. FARGHER and F. L. RYMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 217.

Synthesis of Potential Fungicidal Compounds

K. P. JADHAV and D. B. INGLE

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University,
Aurangabad-431 004.

Manuscript received 19 July 1977, revised 17 October 1977,
accepted 6 December 1977

4-THIAZOLIDINONES are well-known for their amoebicidal¹, hypnotic², anticonvulsant³, mosquito-repellent⁴ properties. It has also been shown to have a deep impact on antithyroid activity⁵ with variation in the structure. The presence of N-C-S linkage in the compound has been shown to have antitubercular⁶, antiradiation⁷, nematocidal⁸ and antifungal activity⁹. 2-Aryl-3-dialkylaminoalkyl-4-thiazolidinones were found to be much more active than procaine which showed anaesthetic activity and some 2-aryl-3-alkylaminoalkyl-4-thiazolidinones have shown activity against sciatic nerve block in guinea pigs and spinal anaesthesia in rabbit¹⁰. 2-Aryl-3-alkyl-4-thiazolidinones were found

to be active against psychomotor, anticonvulsant and barbiturate potentiating activity in mice¹¹. Some of the 2-β-naphthylimino-4-thiazolidinones and their arylethene derivatives have been found to be fungicidal against *Alternaria palanduli*¹². 2-Arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones and their 1,1-dioxides were found to be effective against *Aspergillus niger*¹³. Bhargawa *et al.* have demonstrated that 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones possess considerable fungicidal activity¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Astik *et al.* synthesised 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones and showed that the introduction of -OH group increases the LD₅₀ in mice¹⁷. In view of the significant biological applicability of 4-thiazolidinones, it was thought desirable to synthesise 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethylphenyl)-3-substituted aryl-4-thiazolidinones in order to ascertain effect of substituent in the phenyl nucleus at 3-position of the 4-thiazolidinones on the fungicidal activity against *Helmythosporium appatarnae*, not reported so far.

Experimental

General method of preparation of 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethylphenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinone:

2-Hydroxy-4, 5-dimethyl acetophenone^{18,19} (0.01M), aniline (0.01M) and thioglycolic acid (0.01M) were dissolved in benzene (100 ml) in a round bottomed flask and refluxed with a pinch of ZnCl₂ as a catalyst for 10 hr. Benzene was distilled off. The residue was washed with 2N HCl (10 ml) and then by 10% NaHCO₃ solution (50 ml), except in case of compound Nos. 18, 19, 20 in the Table, washed with water and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. The compounds prepared in 60-70% yield and their physical data are given in the Table.

All the I.R. spectra are taken in nujol mull and showed a sharp absorption peak at 3200-3300 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of free -OH group. A tertiary amide stretching frequency is also exhibited in the range of 1630-1660 cm⁻¹.

Antifungal screening

Antifungal screening of all 4-thiazolidinones was done by dry weight method. In general, the compounds were found to be inhibitory against *H. appatarnae* at 100 ppm. The parent compound and chloro, methyl, methoxy and nitro substituents in the *o*- and *p*- positions of the phenyl nucleus at 3-position showed relatively greater inhibitory effect as compared to the

NOTES

TABLE

Sl. No.	Ar	Mol. formulae	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂ S	77	70	4.77	4.47
2	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ClNO ₂ S	67	65	3.91	4.02
3	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	do	95	62	4.00	4.02
4	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	do	75	68	3.95	4.02
5	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₂ S	67	70	4.10	4.28
6	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	do	90	67	3.95	4.28
7	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	do	77	69	4.59	4.28
8	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₃ S	70	71	3.91	4.08
9	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	do	71	68	4.02	4.08
10	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	do	78	72	4.17	4.08
11	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S	62	63	7.71	7.82
12	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	do	87	68	7.80	7.82
13	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	do	110	66	7.70	7.82
14	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₃ S	80	62	4.01	4.25
15	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	do	65	63	3.80	4.25
16	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	do	72	65	3.95	4.25
17	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrNO ₂ S	73	68	3.29	3.57
18	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ NO ₄ S	68	61	4.12	3.92
19	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	do	72	60	4.01	3.92
20	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	do	80	64	4.00	3.92

*Uncorrected

m-analogue, while compounds having *m*-hydroxy and *m*-carboxy groups were more inhibitory than the *o*- and *p*-isomers probably due to decrease in the acidity of the compounds because of the hydrogen bonding either with nitrogen or oxygen of the thiazolidinone.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. D. S. Mukadam and G. V. Umalkar, Botany Department, Marathwada University, for antifungal screening. One of them (K.P.J.) is thankful to Marathwada University, Aurangabad, for the award of a Junior. Research Fellowship and providing facilities.

References

1. A. R. SURREY and R. A. CUTLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 76, 578.
2. J. DORAN and H. A. SONLE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 193.
3. H. D. TROUTMANN and M. M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3436.
4. W. A. SKINNER, H. H. C. TONG, G. BORDY and T. E. EDWARD, *Chem. Abs.*, (Biochem. Section), 1975, 83, 189351 *t*.
5. L. P. DAMKIV and M. S. AVGUSINOVICH *zb. nauk. pratis L. Vysk. Med. Inst.* 1963, 24, 58, *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 62, 16596 *e*.
6. R. H. MEIZZONI and P. C. ESMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 3471.
7. G. R. HENDRICKS, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 8, 762.
8. J. R. GEISY, *French Patent*, 1965, 1, 395, 069, April 9.
9. J. KINUGAWA and K. NAGASE, *Japanese Patent*, May 4, 1965, 8542; *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 63, 5653h.
10. A. R. SURREY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3354.
11. A. R. SURREY, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 69, 59227g.
12. M. K. RAUT and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2427.
13. V. N. CHOUBEY and H. SINGH, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1970, 43, 2233.
14. P. N. BHARGAWA and I. D. SAXENA, *Vijananana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika (India)*, 1959, 2, 89.
15. P. N. BHARGAWA, K. BHARGAWA and R. C. KAPOOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 23.
16. K. S. L. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, 37, 315.
17. R. R. ASTIK, J. N. ACHARYA, G. B. JOSHI and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 272.
18. K. VON. AUWERS and W. MAUSS, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 1495.
19. S. S. TISWAI and B. N. TIWARI, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 31, 773.